

Large field-of-view two-photon fiberscope offering new insights into left-right turn responsive neurons in freely-behaving mice

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Examining how neurons respond to left-right turn behavior is crucial for understanding spatial navigation, which stands as a fundamental aspect of animal survival and prosperity. In this paper, we report a two-photon (2P) fiberscope of a large field-of-view (FOV) for imaging turn responsive neurons in freely-behaving mice. The fiberscope is compact (of a 2.8 mm outer diameter) and lightweight (1.33 g), allowing mice with a head-mounted fiberscope to perform complex tasks (Figure 1A-B). Our fiberscope adopted an innovative cascaded magnification scheme involving a scanning compound fiber-optic cantilever [1] and a customized micro-objective (Figure 1C). The compound cantilever functions as a pre-focuser for the imaging beam [2], which allows the use of a micro-objective of lower magnification to relay the focused beam from the cantilever to the sample without compromising the overall magnification (or the imaging resolution). The micro-objective offers a low magnification (~ 1) to effectively relay the cantilever tip scanning range to the sample for achieving a large FOV. The customized micro-objective used 2-mm diameter GRIN lenses and a weak diffractive lens (for managing chromatic aberration [3]). Our 2P fiberscope achieved a 1.2 μm /15.9 μm lateral/axial resolution (Figure 1D-E), and a large circular FOV of a 500- μm diameter, enabling sub-cellular resolution imaging of a large number of neurons.

2P fiberscope neuroimaging was conducted in mice when performing T-maze tasks. The large FOV allowed us to image a total population of approximately 390 neurons (Figure 1F), from which we identified 15 left-right turn responsive neurons, as they are segmented and labeled in Figure 1G. Here, left-right turn responsive neurons are defined as those whose calcium activities have a strong correlation to spatial turning behaviors, which were identified by synchronizing the neuron activities to the turning behaviors at T-intersection. The calcium dynamics of the turn responsive neurons are presented by the $\Delta F/F$ traces (Figure 1H), with all calcium spikes (see red dots) and the turning occurrence time points (see green lines) labeled. By imaging the same mouse for 3 days, we consistently observed turn responsive neurons, and the neuron firing probability is calculated by the total neuron firing times versus the total turning times, with the firing probability ranges between 8% - 62% (Figure 1G). Our studies demonstrate that our newly developed 2P fiberscope can consistently image a reliable number of left-right turn responsive neurons within a single FOV in freely-behaving mice, which would be otherwise difficult or unreliable to observe with a 2P probe of a smaller FOV [4, 5]. Our results highlight the significance of using a 2P fiberscope with a large FOV for exploring neural behaviors that underlie complex behaviors.

Figure 1. (A) Photo of a freely-behaving mouse with a head-mounted 2P fiberscope. (B) Photo of the compact 2P fiberscope of a 2.8 mm diameter. (C) Schematic of the large FOV 2P fiberscope consisting of a compound fiber-optic cantilever and a customized micro-objective. (D-E) Point spread functions (PSFs) of the fiberscope acquired by imaging a 200 nm diameter fluorescent microsphere, yielding a lateral and axial resolution of 1.2 μm and 15.9 μm , respectively. (F) A representative image of neurons acquired with a 500 μm FOV, and the image is 10 frame-averaged. (G) Segmentation masks of 15 turn responsive neurons identified in the FOV. (H) Averaged turn responsive neuron number versus firing probability. (I) Calcium dynamics traces of left-right turn responsive neurons. Red dots represent neuron firing peaks and green lines represent turn occurrence time points.

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